

advanced training were discussed, advanced training, advanced training, advanced training, advanced training, advanced training, advanced training, advanced training and advanced training.

At the moment, the traditional approach is low solecca tortish conditions, thriving boetgan tourism dunening tour of the country in the field of finance important bodies, necessary investments and projects of 10% research institute of the organization. If tourism is booming, economy class is easy (for example, ish bilan bandlikning Bishi), unda bir train salbiy sikatlar is exactly emas (for example, ecological sikatlar). Bu esa, tourism functions as a state to provide the order necessary for anglatadi, but bundai orga solish sof izhimoi and the economy of foidalarni time maximal darajada oshirish point of view requires compliance with the requirements of this. During the conversation, the parties expressed satisfaction with the development of cooperation between Tajikistan and China, as well as the development of cooperation between Tajikistan and China. Agrarmas is an integral part (labor activity, composition and interest groups of the leadership of bilan bir ryadda), because the senior lawyer for public education is a source of information. As a result, Solik Yukin optimally evaluated yullarini topish katta actionga EGA bouldi.

Transport and telecommunications have nodalarishlar steamship and temir yul invention, postal communication of its glacial quality, yullarning kengaish tourism rivozhlanish - an important role. Tursunzavod got acquainted with the course and preparation, and also got acquainted with the means that have a special impact on the course, the Raishind hotel, shuningdeck, the European tourist company.

Jahan economics muammolari, zhumladan, tourism bashkarisha tizimini tahillashi-rish masalariga A.S. Alexandrovaning azarlari, M.B. Birzhakova, V.S. Bogolyubova, D.D. Brasnova and bashkalar khorijiy olimlarning bagishlangan research.

Analysis and Methodology

The most dynamically developing form in international trade today is tourism. According to statistics from the World Tourism Organization kura, the number of arrivals of tourists in 2018 amounted to 1.3 billion people . Today, jaxon accounts for 5% of gross domestic product and 30% of jaxon services exports (US \$ 1 trillion per year) to the tourism industry business. According to diagnostic data, kura in 2020, the number of international tourists will increase to 1561 million, and the annual usish barkaror buladi and approximately 4% of the bulishi was predicted (when the coronavirus epidemic is not taken into account).

The diverse socio-economic level of development of Regions has its influence on the development of international tourism in the world. The largest share of the tourist flow is in Europe, and this figure is more than 70% of the tourist market and about 60% of foreign exchange receipts.

The scientific essence of the development of the tourism sector as a sphere of economic activity has a number of features inherent in Uzi. Tourism serves the interests of Man, society as a whole and is a source of income at the micro and macroeconomic levels. Tourism is one of the main factors in creating additional jobs, accelerates the development of road and cocktail building, promotes the production of all kinds of vehicles, serves to preserve folk crafts and national culture of Regions and countries. According to the World Tourism Organization's estimates, the number of tourists by 2020 was projected to be 1.6 billion people, while the 2020 jaxon tourism revenue was projected to exceed \$ 2 trillion.

Results

The main results regarding the role and importance of the development of tourism activities in the national economy show that, according to many scientist-analysts, the following factors are present for the development of tourism in Chalkaro:

1. Economic growth and social progress nafakat business trips, but also travel with cognitive goals, led to the expansion of kilish khajmi.
2. The improvement of all types of Transport made travel cheaper, making it possible for many segments of the population.
3. The increase in the number of hired workers and employees in economically developed countries, an increase in their material and cultural level, strengthened their aspirations for spiritual and educational personnel.
4. Increasing the productivity of labor activity requires strengthening, and more meaningful rest, in which workers receive long, long-term vacations.
5. The development of inter-state relations and cultural exchanges between the States has led to the expansion of ham, Kham interpersonal ties within the khudududis between the two regions.
6. The development of Service Sox encouraged technological progress in telecommunications, increasing interest in visiting various countries and territories.
7. In many countries, reducing restrictions on the removal of currency and the simplification of border formalities encourages the development of ham tourism.

The economic opportunities for the development of tourism at the international level have created the conditions for the development of organizational and economic processes in aloxida countries. International tourism for most of them:

1. The most important source of currency revenue;
2. A factor that stimulates the increase in the balance of Tulov;

As a result of the development of market economy and market relations, the development of conditions for the development of tourism industry in Uzbekistan, the further integration of tourism into the economy of the Republic, in the country's economy, Mukhim akhamiyat is gaining momentum. As you know from the experience of the Jaxon economy, the tourism Sox have a service to ensure the necessary abundant foreign exchange revenue for the treasury of the country, to create new jobs and, together with this, to wait for the standard of living of its morality. With the size of our opportunities in the tourism sphere of the Republic of khalkaro, Kush is radically different from the countries. The geographical urn of Uzbekistan is the one that has a great natural climate, laughing at the state, it holds a great urinalysis in the cultural culture of mankind. Uzbekistan has rare historical architectural monuments, sweet-sugar fruits, a variety of dishes, a magnificent national tradition, a rich mexmondust Hulk with traditions. All this attracts the attention of foreign tourists and makes people lol. Kham Mukhim urin of bulgan political barkaror, who exists in Uzbekistan in the development of tourism in khalkaro.

At present, there are more than 450 tourist firms in the Republic, the process of their work is controlled by a National Company. As we know, for the development of tourism in the experience of jaxon, iconic models are enslaved: management from the center, market and ways of monetar development.

The contribution of tourism to the country's economy, the development of the service sector and the employment of the population lag behind the world average. In order to develop the tourism economy in our country, a number of tasks and priorities have been set:

- formation of favorable conditions for the activities of the subjects of the tourism industry, elimination of all obstacles and gaps in the development of Tourism, simplification of visa and registration procedures, passport and customs control;
- implementation of comprehensive measures to ensure the safety of life and health of tourists and yekskursants in the organization of tourism services;
- new potential types of Tourism-intensive development of pilgrimage, environmental, educational, yetnographic, gastronomic, Sports, treatment-wellness, rural, industrial, business, Children, Youth and family tourism;
- expansion of cooperation in the field of tourism with international and national organizations, large foreign brands and companies, introduction of advanced world quality standards for the provision of tourism service;
- modern facilities of tourism infrastructure in the regions of the Republic, first of all hotels, transport and logistics structures, intensive development of engineering and communication infrastructure, wide involvement of foreign investment for these purposes;
- development of competitive tourism products, creation of new tourism destinations in the regions, bringing them to the world tourism markets;
- radical improvement of the quality training system of qualified personnel for the tourism sector.

Completely abandoning the Administrative-Command-based management system in the economy, the gradual implementation of market reforms and careful consideration of monetary policy ensured macroeconomic stability, high-speed growth of the economy, the maintenance of inflation at the level of forecast indicators and served to create wide opportunities and favorable conditions for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, farm movement.

At the same time, an in-depth analysis of the path of development that our country has taken, today the world market conjuncture is changing dramatically, and the growing competition in the context of globalization requires a completely new approach and the development and realization of principles for the development of our state at a more stable and accelerated pace. Uzbekistan is becoming increasingly popular among tourists due to its rich cultural and historical heritage, hospitable people. To date, structural changes in the world economy indicate the rapid development of the services sector, while the growing contribution of tourism creates the need to assess the same proportion. At the end of the 19th century, statistics in the field of tourism were observed for the first time in Austria, and earlier in Switzerland in 1852 the issue of drawing up official statistics of tourism was put in the middle. For the first time in the 19th and 20th centuries, scientific research was carried out on about 21 topics related to tourism in foreign countries, including the famous, outstanding Austrian scientist, who widely used statistics on tourism in his scientific views. An obvious example of this is Engelman's scientific research as a model. It is worth noting that countries such as Austria, Switzerland, France, Canada, Spain, Sweden, Great Britain, the United States have led the development of reports on the share of tourism in the national

economy, Economic Research in the field of Tourism. For the last 50 years, the research work of the tourism sector has been developing rapidly, but it can be observed that the problems of the tourism economy are studied by scientists, compared to the study of other areas of economic activity. One of the most important scientific investigations into tourism was in mid-1960 by M. Clouson I Dj. Under kletch's name, "recreational Economics in nature", and in 1970, H.P.Gray's scientific electronic journal "International Tourism and" Economics and innovative technologies". # 6, November-December, 2016 www.iqtisodiyot.uz the connection between trade" is the publication of his books. This, in turn, aroused the interest of economists in the study of tourism as a separate type of economic activity. In 1995, for the first time, the scientific journal "Tourism Economics" () began to be published, which reflects the economic and financial problems of tourism on a global scale. This is a sign that tourism, like the others, is increasing in its role in the world economy. At the same time, the processes of the financial and economic crisis in the world continue, tourism plays an important role in the solution of such urgent issues as ensuring the stability of the economy, increasing social welfare, improving the development of the services sector and the quality of living standards of the population, wide involvement of foreign currencies, creation of additional jobs, as well as strengthening At present, tourism is important as an important high-income sector of the rapidly developing economy, unlike some sectors, in that it does not lead to a decrease in natural resources, and this sector is an export-oriented activity, with resistance to instability in the world market. For many countries, the tourism industry is the main component of the diversification of exports. Tourism is currently considered a high - income sector, and new directions of tourism are emerging. . In conclusion, it should be said that despite the ongoing processes of the global financial and economic crisis, the international tourism industry is developing at the same time, which is especially noticeable in countries with a high role and potential for tourism in its economy, and with a regular increase in the flow of tourism on a global scale, it is affecting international tourism exports .

In particular, there is a shortage of hotel places in Karakalpakstan, Andijan and Kashkadarya. Great opportunities are not used in Navoi, Jizzakh, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya and Tashkent regions. There are very few tourist services suitable for young people. Work on the introduction of" family "and" inside all " services is slow.

Of the 206 thermal and mineral water springs in the regions, 18 are in use. For example, the temperature of the water of the Arashan lakes, located on the whiplash pass, is in the winter-summer 36-degree heat and does not lag behind foreign resorts. Or, it is possible to organize sanatoriums-resorts around thermal springs that come out from under the ground at a temperature of 40-70 degrees Celsius in Chimboy, blackberries and blackberries.

The potential of 122 museums in our country is also not used in attracting tourists. It contains more than 2,500,000 objects, of which 112,000 are also unique to world history and culture .

Boysun has a burrow cave, considered one of the deepest caves in the world, where a Neanderthal human remnant was found, Uzundara Castle, a monument of the ancient ellin culture. The nature of the district, the climate is also excellent. It attracts 500,000 tourists by setting up a hotel, camping, "dor Road", tourist houses.

Such opportunities are also found in the villages of Tovoqsoy in Bostanliq, Ovjasoy in Ohangaron, Yangiabad in Angren, Miraki in Shahrisabz, Nanay in Yangikurgon, Chodak in pop. It was also noted that bathing zones could be established in Ashshikul in Nukus, Zikrikul in Bukhara, Aydarkul and Tuzkon Lake in Jizzakh, just like in the cattle.

Along the "highway of Tourism of Uzbekistan", along the roads passing through 31 districts and urban areas, it is necessary to build "caravanserais" covering services such as parking, camping, car service, catering, refueling.

186 different international and local festivals are organized in our country. Through them, there is an opportunity to attract an additional 1 million foreign and 5 million domestic tourists. Officials were instructed to organize these events at a high level and safely, to promote them widely around the world. In this year, the establishment of additional weekends on the occasion of the Navruz holiday, the issuance of a discount in 250 hotels and museums, the free availability of visiting objects, gave a great impetus to domestic tourism. Thanks to this, an additional 110 thousand local tourists went to Bukhara and Samarkand. We will also be given another 5-day rest to our people in connection with the Ramadan Eid next week.

Conclusion

From September 1, a system will be introduced to return to citizens traveling around the country 15% of the cost of air, rail and bus tickets, 20% of the cost of the hotel, 50% of the cost of tickets to museums and other cultural objects.

The effective organization of the activities of museums is also important in the development of Tourism. Therefore, after a complete correspondence of all museum exhibits on the Republic, instructions were given to create their electronic base, improve the skills of the heads and employees of museums.

Only 1 percent of the exhibits were put on display due to the low exhibition space of the museums. In addition, residents do not have the opportunity to go to distant museums. Therefore, it was said that under the program "bringing art closer to the people", it is necessary to organize portable exhibitions of museums in the regions. The task was set to transform more than 4,500 archaeological monuments in our country into open-air museums.

One of the most important means of organizing tourists is transport. Currently, the high cost of transportation remains one of the main obstacles in attracting foreign tourists. There are not many "low-costers" on international and local routes. To get a ticket to the modern train "Afrosiyob", it is necessary to apply a few weeks in advance.

Therefore, the Ministry of Transport was instructed to improve transport infrastructure in the tourism sector.

In order to meet the demand of tourists for air travel, from July 1, discounts of up to 50 percent will be introduced on services provided to foreign airlines under the "pilgrimage tourism" program. By October 1, a new company "Silk Air" will be created, aimed at domestic airliners. Thousands of foreigners visit Uzbekistan every year, and their number is growing just as the country's prestige among investors and tourists is growing. Accordingly, it is necessary to book in advance. Booking online will simplify your trip, taking into account the tastes and desires of everyone, we guarantee a comfortable stay in the country on the sleeve. You just need to indicate the location and the optimal price, and we, in turn, provide you with

a list of suitable hotels. It offers a wide range of hotels in Uzbekistan, as well as tours throughout Uzbekistan, tours in Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shahrisabz, Fergana, Marghilon, Rishton, Kokand and many other cities in Uzbekistan. All this has shown that the importance of the tourism industry in the economic life of our country is growing. This testifies to the fact that yesa, in turn, occupies a place in the international tourism market of Uzbekistan. In conclusion, it should be noted that in order to develop the tourism economy of each country, it is necessary to allocate funds to the Una to expand the market for tourism services, establish tourist clusters, and create many vacancies for the needs of the population.

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